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To whom it may concern

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Subject: Research Impact Testimonial regarding Dr. Luigi Vanfretti's contributions to power system dynamic information exchange and ENTSO-E's Common Grid Model Exchange Standards

Dear Sirs,

This document serves as testimonial of the research contributions of Dr. Luigi Vanfretti and his research group (SmarTS Lab) at KTH Royal Institute of Technology, to be used as supporting documentation for "impact assessments" in grant or institutional evaluations.

I learned about Dr. Vanfretti's early regarding power system information exchange, modeling and simulation through a dissemination workshop of the FP7 iTesla project in January 2014, and shortly after in the CIM (Common Information Model) Users Group meeting in Oslo in June 2014. In addition, I have had further exposure of Dr. Vanfretti's and his team work through their interactions with ENTSO-E, and their participation in the ENTSO-E Interoperability test (IOP) regarding CGMES (Common Grid Model Exchange Standard/Specification) and the activities leading to this IOP test.

As a team lead in ENTSO-E I covered most of the activities related to the one of ENTSO-E's major projects - CGMES/CIM¹. I have been involved in these activities for the last almost 10 years. In parallel I have been leading the support to the research and innovation activities and this gave me the opportunity to get in touch with the iTesla project and follow up on their recommendations, which is fully in line with the ENTSO-E R&I strategy.

- Societal Importance: The Integrated European Electricity System

ENTSO-E, the European Network of Transmission System Operators, represents 42 electricity transmission system operators (TSOs) from 35 countries across Europe. ENTSO-E was established and given legal mandates by the EU's Third Legislative Package for the Internal Energy Market in 2009, which aims at further liberalizing the gas and electricity markets in the EU.

The integration of renewable energy sources (RES), which is a major target of the EU's energy and climate policy objectives for 2020 and beyond, will affect existing electricity grid infrastructure, operations and the functioning of the electricity market itself. The integration of renewables into the power system requires for their intermittency to be balanced. This can be tackled by electricity grids operating smartly and cost-efficiently. To do this, a seamless and efficient information exchange is necessary at various stages, between an increasing number of companies – TSOs, DSOs, generators etc.

- Industrial Importance: Information Exchange Efforts at ENTSO-E

¹ ENTSO-E CIM website: <https://www.entsoe.eu/major-projects/common-information-model-cim/Pages/default.aspx>

Such information exchanges have become indispensable in long-term system planning, operational planning including real-time information on the generation output, balancing control, etc. and market (generation schedules, trades, balancing resource management, etc.).

To meet data exchanges' needs for such purposes it is required that TSOs, third parties and service providers to use commonly agreed and compatible data exchange formats, in our case standards based on the IEC Common Information Model (CIM).

ENTSO-E is playing a driving role in establishing, maintaining and further developing such information exchange standards, ensuring that these standards are developed in line with TSO requirements and are compatible with third parties and service providers.

In addition, ENTSO-E plays a leading role in organizing CIM interoperability tests related to both grid model and market exchanges. There are at least two types of interoperability test:

- Tests to validate a CIM standard as a part of the standard's development process;
- Tests to validate the conformity of available software solutions with an approved standard.

The ENTSO-E CIM interoperability tests facilitate the development of CIM standards for both ENTSO-E and IEC. These IOP tests are tailored to ensure adequate representation of important business requirements for TSOs. The tests are also designed to allow vendors to verify the correctness of the interpretation of the CIM standards. The tests directly support ENTSO-E processes towards achieving the objectives of the EU Third Energy Package.

- Summary of Research Results and their Impact

Within the FP7 iTesla project² and the ITEA3 openCPS project³, Dr. Vanfretti and his team have greatly contributed to the development of new concepts, methods and tools that have effectively aided ENTSO-E's in the development of Information Exchange Standards.

These contributions directly address the needs for the information exchange of power system dynamics, methods for simulation and model validation have been reported in highly recognized conferences and journal publications, but more importantly, have been distributed as Open Source Software (OSS). More specifically, the following contributions have been directly used by the CIM related activities in ENTSO-E.

The first result of Dr. Luigi Vanfretti that is to be highlight, was his work in demonstrating the potential of the Modelica language for unambiguous exchange [1] of computer models of power system components between different simulation tools while preserving the same simulated response and without any need of re-implementation provided that the tools comply with the Modelica standard. Based on these results, within the EU FP7 iTesla project, Dr. Vanfretti lead the development of a Modelica library to simulate power systems with different project partners [2]. The library was released as OSS, making it available for the public at large, and reported in the SoftwareX journal [3]. Dr. Vanfretti's team continues to develop the library, which can be found online at: <https://github.com/SmarTS-Lab/OpenIPSL>

Parallel to this work, Dr. Vanfretti's team started to address the issue of how to link CIM and Modelica for consistent power system model exchange and simulation [4] and how this can help decoupling the power system dynamic model from simulation tools [5].

² iTesla project website: <http://www.itesla-project.eu/>

³ openCPS website: <https://itea3.org/project/opencps.html>

These results gave the necessary input to ENTSO-E in the development of a document⁴ that explains how Modelica models can be linked to the Common Grid Model Exchange Standard (CGMES), which is now part of the CGMES v2.5 documentations (Annex F)⁵.

The ability to couple the mathematical models defined in the Modelica language with CIM as now specified in the CGMES v2.5 standard implies that IOP tests have to be carried out to assess conformance to the standard. The latest IOP took place on July 2016, and Dr. Vanfretti and his team contributed to the IOP efforts.

In this regard, Dr. Luigi Vanfretti was instrumental in providing support to ENTSO-E by helping bringing Modelica experts to give an introduction to the Modelica language and the state of the art in the simulation technology, as well as participating himself in the webinar providing an overview of the OpenIPSL library and a Hands-on-Tutorial to use the library⁶. This tutorial aimed at helping different parties involved in the development of CGMES to understand the Modelica language and the features of the available library.

In addition, and also related to the IOP Tests, Dr. Vanfretti's team developed the Modelica model used in the IOP tests using the OpenIPSL library⁷. This serves as the basis for future work in IOP tests for this part of the standard, and are available also as part of the OSS distribution of OpenIPSL: <https://github.com/SmarTS-Lab/OpenIPSL/tree/master/OpenIPSL/Examples/Controls/CGMES/ES>

Finally, Dr. Vanfretti's team has developed a completely novel tool for the validation of dynamic model called RaPID (Rapid Parameter Identification Toolbox), that can be exploited by different TSOs to enhance the quality of the mathematical models representing their components and grids by comparing them to measured physical responses [6,7]. This software is also distributed as OSS, and can be found at: https://github.com/SmarTS-Lab/iTesla_RaPID

- Research Impact

It is important to underline that Dr. Vanfretti's effort in materializing research results as Open Source Software, mainly OpenIPSL but also RaPID. These software-s are not only accessible to the general public at large, but are also released with an OSS License, which means that future work (by any other researchers) can be started based on this foundation.

Adopting the OSS Licensing model is commendable and rare in the electrical power industry, thereby setting an important precedent on how research can directly contribute to the Open Science⁸ goals of the European Commission and have a direct impact in supporting EC's policies, in this case, the ones related to ENTSO-E and the CIM.

- Educational Impact

Dr. Luigi Vanfretti has made substantial contributions on training researchers in both the FP7 iTesla project⁹ and now in the openCPS project. More than 10 MSc students carried out their thesis in the period of 2013-2015 in the area of power system simulation and model validation, and there are currently 4 PhD students developing new methods and concepts to exploit the results further.

⁴ ENTSO-E, "Use of Modelica in the Dynamics profile of the CGMES version 2.4," Version 2, January 31, 2016.

⁵ Common Grid Model Exchange Specification (CGMES), Version 2.5, Draft IEC 61970-600 Part, Edition 2. Document version 1: July 8 2016 which will be published as draft in Sep 2016.

⁶ Tutorial on Youtube: <https://youtu.be/H6h9s4iMzA8?t=3703>

⁷ ENTSO-E, "Modelica tests – background," Version 1 – IOP 2016, 22 June 2016.

⁸ Open Science: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/open-science>

⁹ MSc Thesis in the FP7 iTesla Project: <http://www.itesla-project.eu/msc-thesis>

In addition, Dr. Vanfretti has made a clear effort to disseminate his educational materials in the internet, making available hands-on tutorials for both the OpenIPSL and RaPIId that have been given in conferences, and can be found online:

- OpenIPSL Tutorial:
 - https://github.com/SmarTS-Lab/OpenIPSL/tree/master/Application%20Examples/_Tutorial
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H6h9s4iMzA8>
- RaPIId Tutorial:
 - https://github.com/SmarTS-Lab/iTesla_RaPIId/releases/tag/Tuto_ModProd_2016

As one of the leaders working on a major ENTSO-E project within the area of expertise of Dr. Vanfretti, and from the arguments provided above, I believe that continued support for Dr. Luigi Vanfretti's research will result in applicable and exploitable results by the ENTSO-E community at large.

Dr. Vanfretti's contributions will help to bring forward ENTSO-E's efforts on interoperability, and directly support ENTSO-E processes towards achieving the objectives of the EU Third Energy Package.

As I am currently changing position you can further contact Mr. Marcos Olmos (marcos.olmos@entsoe.eu) or Mr. Dario Frazzetta (Dario.frazzetta@entsoe.eu) who will both follow up on CIM/CGMES related activities. I remain available for any further clarifications related to the work of Dr. Luigi Vanfretti in supporting Modelica and CGMES development. You can reach me at +49 151 67 434 432 or ch.ivanov@gmail.com.

I wish Dr. Luigi Vanfretti all the best in his work and I hope to be able to cooperate with him again in the future.

Yours sincerely,

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